

On the Challenges of Fully Incremental Neural Dependency Parsing

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Abstract

Since the popularization of BiLSTMs and Transformer-based bidirectional encoders, state-of-the-art syntactic parsers have lacked incrementality, requiring access to the whole sentence and deviating from human language processing. This paper explores whether fully incremental dependency parsing with modern architectures can be competitive. We build parsers combining strictly left-to-right neural encoders with fully incremental sequence-labeling and transition-based decoders. The results show that fully incremental parsing with modern architectures considerably lags behind bidirectional parsing, noting the challenges of psycholinguistically plausible parsing.

1 Introduction

Human understanding of natural language is widely agreed to be *incremental*: humans do not need to read a complete sentence to start understanding it. Instead, we update partial interpretations as we receive more input (Marslen-Wilson, 1985).

While the exact way in which this incrementality works is still unclear (Kitaev et al., 2022), its presence implies that some form of incrementality is an obvious necessary condition for a parser to be psycholinguistically plausible as a model of human processing (Miller and Schuler, 2010). Since human processing is the gold standard for automatic parsing, we know that it should be possible to achieve accurate parsing with incremental systems. Yet, in recent years, none of the competitive syntactic parsers that have been proposed for either of the main syntactic formalisms can be said to be incremental, even under the loosest possible definitions of the term. This poses challenges in the intersection between syntax and computational psycholinguistics, e.g., use cases both for modeling of human parsing and for real-time settings where one wants partial results before waiting for a sentence to end. Currently, most parsers use bidirectional encoders, such as BiLSTMs (Kiperwasser

and Goldberg, 2016; Dozat and Manning, 2017) or Transformers (Zhou and Zhao, 2019; Mrini et al., 2020; Yang and Deng, 2020), so the whole sentence is being used before even processing the first word. An exception is the constituent parser by Kitaev et al. (2022), who use a fully incremental encoder, but the rest of the model is bidirectional, as it uses Transformer layers and a CYK-like, non-left-to-right span-based decoder (Stern et al., 2017).

This paper explores the viability of *fully incremental* dependency parsing, i.e., parsers where all the components (from the encoder to the decoder) work *strictly* from left to right. To our knowledge, this is the first attempt to build fully incremental dependency parsers with modern deep learning architectures.

2 Incrementality in Parsing

In transition-based parsing Transition-based parsing has traditionally been linked to incrementality (Nivre, 2008), as it works from left to right and builds partial outputs. Some authors consider that transition-based parsers as a whole are incremental, as they have internal states with partial outputs (Eisape et al., 2022). We will call this criterion *weak incrementality*. Others exclude algorithms like the arc-standard dependency parser, where dependencies are not built in left-to-right order and input arbitrarily far in the future might be needed to build right-branching dependencies (Christiansen and Chater, 2016). We will call this stricter view *strong incrementality*, and formalize it as follows: given a monotonic parser (i.e., one where each partial parse is a superset of the previous), we say that it is *strongly incremental with delay k* if every possible partial parse for a prefix $w_1 \dots w_{i-k}$ can be built upon reading the prefix $w_1 \dots w_i$, without the parser having accessed the rest of the input.¹ Analo-

¹The definition of a partial parse for the prefix $w_1 \dots w_{i-k}$ depends on the grammatical formalism. For dependency parsing, we mean the subgraph of a full parse induced by the nodes

gous considerations about the limitations with right-branching in weak incrementality, and parsers that try to avoid it to various extents, have been studied in the CCG literature (Ambati et al., 2015; Stanojević and Steedman, 2019, 2020; Stanojević et al., 2021). Contrary to arc-standard, other transition-based dependency parsers are strongly incremental: the arc-eager (Nivre, 2003), Covington (Covington, 2001) or multiplanar (Gómez-Rodríguez and Nivre, 2013) parsers all fit our definition above.

Classic implementations of strongly incremental parsers typically have positive delay (Beuck et al., 2011) between input and output due to lookahead. Some approaches have considered zero delay, albeit with weaker performance (Köhn and Menzel, 2013). Solutions are also available for speculation in incremental parsing (Kitaev et al., 2022), by introducing non-monotonicity (Honnibal et al., 2013; Fernández-González and Gómez-Rodríguez, 2017).

Thus, the paradigm supports incrementality and many implementations of these parsers from the pre-deep-learning era, which did not use contextualized encoders, were strongly incremental, leading to the observation by Gómez-Rodríguez (2016) that at that point, some state-of-the-art parsing models were converging with psycholinguistically plausible models. However, in recent years bidirectional encoders have become ubiquitous, ruling out even weak incrementality from recent implementations of transition-based parsers, be them for dependency or other grammatical formalisms (Kiperwasser and Goldberg, 2016; Stanojević and Steedman, 2019; Fernandez Astudillo et al., 2020; Fernández-González and Gómez-Rodríguez, 2023). In this respect, it is worth mentioning that the approach by Yang and Deng (2020) is described as “strongly incremental constituency parsing” but this refers to the decoder, as they use a bidirectional encoder. The only recent proposal we are aware of that aims for incrementality in the whole system is the CCG parser by Stanojević and Steedman (2020), also a constituency parser, but its labelled F-score is over 7 points lower than a non-incremental baseline in an English-only evaluation.

In label-based parsing Other parsing paradigms that yield themselves to incrementality, as they

in $w_1 \dots w_{i-k}$. Some authors require connectedness (Beuck et al., 2011). However, since the path between two words in $w_1 \dots w_{i-k}$ in the final parse may involve words outside the prefix, we do not believe this requirement is necessary.

could work from left to right, are seq2seq parsing (Vinyals et al., 2015) and sequence-labeling parsing (Gómez-Rodríguez and Vilares, 2018; Strzyz et al., 2019). However, for the former, we are not aware of any implementation without bidirectional encoders. For the latter, while there are strongly incremental sequence-labeling decoders for both constituency (Gómez-Rodríguez and Vilares, 2018) and dependency (Strzyz et al., 2020), most implementations use bidirectional encoders as well. The exception are some experiments with feed-forward encoders in Gómez-Rodríguez and Vilares (2018), using a sliding window to model near future context (and thus, with delay). Yet, their F-score is 14 points below their non-incremental counterparts in the same paper, and almost 20 below the overall state of the art.

3 Incremental models

The research question arises whether it is possible to have competitive incremental dependency parsers in the neural era. We take the first step and test how mainstream approaches would work in a setting of strong incrementality. In our work, we will focus on models with *strictly* zero delay, but we also evaluate less strict setups, in particular with delays 1 and 2. To do so, we will rely on modern encoder-decoder models. All source code is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/anaezquerro/incpar>).

3.1 Incremental encoders

Let $w = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{|w|}]$ (with $w_i \in \mathcal{V}$) be an input sentence. An encoder can be seen as a parameterized function $\Omega_{\theta, |w|} : \mathcal{V}^{|w|} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}^{|w|}$, where \mathcal{V} is the input vocabulary space, and $\mathcal{H} \in \mathcal{R}^N$ is the hidden representational space in where each w_i is projected. In this work we are particularly interested in incremental encoders, i.e., those where given a token w_i , the computation of its projected representation h_i only needs the sub-sequence $w_{[1:i]}$. We consider different encoders for this purpose: (i) **4 stacked left-to-right LSTMs** (Hochreiter and Schmidhuber, 1997), where input is a concatenation of a word and PoS tag vector (random init) and a char-level unidirectional LSTM; (ii) **BLOOM** (Scao et al., 2022) (due to resource constraints, we run the smallest version with 560M parameters); and (iii) **mGPT** (Shliazhko et al., 2022).

As *control* encoders (upper bound baselines), we use non-incremental encoders: (i) bidirectional

LSTMs (same setup as for left-to-right LSTMs), and (ii) XLM-RoBERTa (Conneau et al., 2020).

3.2 Incremental decoders

We consider incremental (i) sequence labeling parsing, and (ii) transition-based parsing decoders.

3.2.1 Sequence labeling decoders

A sequence labeling decoder is a parametrized function $\Phi_{\theta, |w|}: \mathcal{H}^{|w|} \rightarrow \mathcal{L}^{|w|}$, which maps each hidden vector ($h_i \in \mathcal{H}$) outputted by a generic encoder into an output label $l_i \in \mathcal{L}$ that represents a part of the output parse. As the decoder, we use a 1-layered feed-forward network and a softmax. As for label encodings, we select representatives from two encoding families (Strzyz et al., 2019, 2020):

Head-based We study three variants, all of them supporting non-projective trees. First, the absolute-indexing encoding (abs-idx), where the token labels are the index of their head. Second, the relative-indexing encoding (rel-idx), where the label is the difference between the head and dependent indexes. Third, the PoS-tag-based encoding (PoS-idx), where each label is encoded as an offset that indicates that the n th word to its left/right with a given PoS tag is the head.²

Strings of brackets First, we consider the 1-planar bracketing encoding (1p), where the label for each token is represented using a string of brackets, with each arc represented by a bracket pair. This encoding can only model crossing arcs in opposite directions. To tackle this, there is a 2-planar variant (2p), analogous, but defining a second plane of brackets.

In the context of full incrementality, we will say that an encoding is *forward-looking* if a label for a token w_i can refer to some token to the right of w_i . The abs-idx, rel-idx and PoS-idx encodings are forward-looking (e.g., with abs-idx, the word w_2 could have 4 as its label, meaning that its head is w_4 , which has not been read yet); while the bracketing encodings are *not* forward-looking. Forward-lookingness does not break incrementality: all the considered encodings are still strongly incremental with delay 0 (all dependencies involving $w_1 \dots w_i$ can be retrieved from the labels $l_1 \dots l_i$). However,

²The PoS-tag based encoding needs PoS tags for decoding the sequence of labels to a tree. Instead of introducing PoS-tag information in those models, our PoS-tag-based decoders predict in multitask learning both the syntactic label and PoS tag associated to each word, in order to remove bias with respect to other encodings.

one could expect forward-looking encodings to suffer more from using incremental encoders, due to needing to make decisions involving future words that the system cannot yet access.

In our implementation, for models with delay zero, the i th label is predicted directly from h_i . For models with delay $k > 0$, labels are predicted from a concatenated representation $h_i \dots h_{i+k-1} \cdot h_{i+k}$.

It is also worth noting that the obtention of the tree encoded by a sequence labeling encoding can require simple postprocessing heuristics (e.g. to remove cycles in head-selection encodings). This does not break incrementality, as these heuristics are applicable to partial outputs as well.

3.2.2 Transition-based decoders

A transition-based decoder is defined as a tuple (C, T, c_s, C_t) , where C is a set of configurations (or parsing states) with associated partial parses, T a set of transitions between states, and c_s and C_t are the initial state and set of valid final states, respectively. In the case of the arc-eager parser (Nivre, 2008), states are triplets of the form (σ, β, A) where σ is a stack of partially processed words, β a buffer of remaining words³ which always takes the form $\beta_i = w_i \dots w_{|w|}$ for some i , and A is the partial parse at that state. This parser is strongly incremental, as the way in which the algorithm constructs dependencies (in a strictly left-to-right manner) means that a configuration with buffer β_i can hold every possible partial parse for the prefix $w_1 \dots w_i$. The parser’s delay depends on the number of buffer words used as lookahead features in the implementation. In our case, this is only one (we only use the first stack word and the first buffer word) so we can obtain partial parses for $w_1 \dots w_i$ accessing only $w_1 \dots w_i$, hence the delay is 0. Equivalently to sequence-labeling decoders, for models with delay $k > 0$, we access a concatenated vector of the form $w_i \dots w_{i+k-1} \cdot w_{i+k}$. For prediction of transitions, we again use a 1-layered feed-forward network.

4 Experiments

We choose 12 diverse treebanks from UD 2.11 (Nivre et al., 2020), supported by the tested LLMs. We test all possible combinations of encoders and decoders. As a well-known baseline, we use the biaffine (DM; Dozat and Manning, 2017) parser

³Buffer words are often described as “unread” words when describing the algorithm, but for incrementality purposes we need to count them as “accessed” if they are used as features, as the parser implementation is using them for prediction.

in *supar*. We use unlabelled attachment score (UAS) for evaluation. Labelled (LAS) results and individual treebank results are in Appendix A.

Table 1 shows an aggregated summary of the results with strict delay zero. It shows that fully incremental models considerably lag behind their counterparts with bidirectional (control) encoders: the best fully incremental model for each language is 11.2 UAS points behind on average (sd: 5.0) with respect to the corresponding best control model. There is large inter-linguistic variability, Telugu (te_{MTG}) being especially amenable to incremental processing, 5.3 UAS points behind, and the opposite for Chinese (zh_{GSD}), 23.1 points behind. Our incremental-decoder-only models with LLMs as encoders are competitive against the BiLSTM-based version of the baseline (BiLSTM encoder, biaffine decoder), surpassing it on 7 out of 12 languages. However, they are a few points behind with respect to a version of the biaffine parser using RoBERTa encodings (which can be taken as a state-of-the-art system), consistent with existing comparisons of sequence-labeling parsers and biaffine parsers (Anderson and Gómez-Rodríguez, 2021). Put together, this seems to suggest that the challenge of incrementality falls mostly on the encoding side. If we focus on comparing different strongly incremental models we see that, as expected, forward-looking encodings suffer greatly from incremental encoders.

Table 2 compares the results from Table 1 against the corresponding models using delays 1 and 2. Improvements are consistent across the board. Interestingly, moving from delay 0 to 1 already shows a clear and large increase in robustness, especially for forward-looking encodings: the average gap between these and non-forward-looking encodings goes from over 10 points with delay 0 to nonexistent with delay 1, although considerable gaps remain in some languages like Chinese (zh_{GSD}) or English (en_{EWT}).

Finally, Figure 1 complements Table 2 with an analysis of the F-score with respect to dependency displacement (signed distance) for English and Chinese, chosen because they yielded the largest improvements when using positive delay. In particular, the figure shows that the lower performance of delay zero models is mainly due to poor performance of forward-looking encodings on leftward dependencies (right half of figure), and that a small positive delay already translates into clear improve-

	Fully incremental			Incremental decoder			DM	
	fl	non-fl	tb	fl	non-fl	tb	↔	∞
af _{PADT}	75.7 _R →	76.8 _{IP} ↔	79.6 _↔ *	84.6 _R ↔	88.0 _{2P} ↔	86.9 _↔	86.9	91.0
eu _{BDT}	62.0 _P ↔	73.0 _{IP} ↔	71.0 _↔	87.0 _R ↔	87.6 _{2P} ↔	86.6 _↔	88.2	88.6
zh _{GSD}	51.1 _R ↔	64.4 _{2P} ↔	64.1 _↔	83.4 _R ↔	87.5 _{IP} ↔	85.3 _↔	86.7	90.7
en _{EWT}	61.5 _P ↔	74.7 _{2P} ↔	72.9 _↔	90.1 _R ↔	91.6 _{IP} ↔	89.5 _↔	90.2	92.7
fr _{GSD}	70.9 _R ↔	84.4 _{IP} ↔	84.7 _↔	92.3 _A ↔	94.7 _{2P} ↔	91.6 _↔	93.5	95.0
hi _{HDTB}	67.1 _P ↔	83.5 _{IP} ↔	83.2 _↔	94.3 _A ↔	95.3 _{2P} ↔	93.8 _↔	95.5	95.7
id _{GSD}	73.0 _R ↔	77.9 _{IP} ↔	78.6 _↔	84.5 _R ↔	86.3 _{2P} ↔	85.1 _↔	88.5	89.6
mr _{FUFAL}	64.1 _P ↔	69.7 _{2P} ↔	65.8 _↔	75.7 _R ↔	75.2 _{IP} ↔	76.0 _↔	79.2	81.7
es _{ANC}	67.9 _R ↔	83.2 _{2P} ↔	82.9 _↔	92.0 _A ↔	93.4 _{IP} ↔	91.2 _↔	93.1	94.3
ta _{TTB}	59.1 _P ↔	67.3 _{IP} ↔	69.7 _↔	71.4 _↔	75.8 _{IP} ↔	78.6 _↔	77.2	80.0
te _{MTG}	73.8 _P ↔	85.0 _{2P} ↔	80.4 _↔	89.9 _R ↔	90.3 _{2P} ↔	89.0 _↔	89.2	94.5
vi _{VTB}	57.3 _R ↔	64.5 _{2P} ↔	64.5 _↔	72.7 _R ↔	74.1 _{IP} ↔	76.0 _↔	77.0	80.2
μ	65.3	75.4	74.8	84.8	84.6	85.8	87.1	89.5

Table 1: UAS scores paired with best forward looking (**fl**) and non-forward looking (**non-fl**) encodings, and transition-based (**tb**) decoder. Superscripts denote the encoder-decoder pair: LSTM (→), BLOOM-560m (*), mGPT (↔), BiLSTM (↔), XLM-RoBERTa (∞). Subscripts denote the best performing encoding: absolute (A), relative (R), PoS-tag-based (P), 1-planar (1P) and 2-planar (2P). Macro-average (μ) and baseline performance (**DM**, for Dozat and Manning) with different encoders (↔, ∞) are included. Language abbreviations come from ISO 639-1 (Table 19 in the Appendix).

	Fully incremental delay 1			Fully incremental delay 2		
	fl	non-fl	tb	fl	non-fl	tb
af _{PADT}	84.2 _{+8.5} ^P ↔	80.2 _{+3.4} ^{2P} ↔	79.9 _{+0.3} [↔]	83.9 _{+8.2} ^P ↔	82.9 _{+6.1} ^{IP} ↔	80.0 _{+0.4} [↔]
eu _{BDT}	78.4 _{+16.4} ^P ↔	76.9 _{+3.9} ^{IP} ↔	75.7 _{+4.7} [↔]	80.0 _{+18.0} ^P ↔	80.1 _{+7.1} ^{IP} ↔	76.9 _{+5.9} [↔]
zh _{GSD}	64.3 _{+13.2} ^P ↔	73.5 _{+9.1} ^{2P} ↔	72.8 _{+8.7} [↔]	68.4 _{+17.3} ^P ↔	74.8 _{+10.4} ^{2P} ↔	75.6 _{+11.5} [↔]
en _{EWT}	81.9 _{+20.4} ^P ↔	88.1 _{+13.4} ^{IP} ↔	83.3 _{+10.4} [↔]	85.0 _{+24.1} ^P ↔	88.7 _{+14.0} ^{IP} ↔	85.2 _{+12.3} [↔]
fr _{GSD}	84.4 _{+15.5} ^P ↔	86.2 _{+1.8} ^{2P} ↔	87.5 _{+2.8} [↔]	87.6 _{+16.7} ^P ↔	89.2 _{+4.8} ^{IP} ↔	86.7 _{+2.0} [↔]
hi _{HDTB}	82.5 _{+15.4} ^P ↔	86.2 _{+2.7} ^{IP} ↔	88.7 _{+5.5} [↔]	85.8 _{+18.7} ^P ↔	90.1 _{+6.6} ^{IP} ↔	88.9 _{+5.7} [↔]
id _{GSD}	80.8 _{+7.8} ^P ↔	80.4 _{+2.5} ^{IP} ↔	79.2 _{+0.6} [↔]	81.9 _{+8.9} ^P ↔	82.1 _{+4.2} ^{IP} ↔	79.0 _{+1.0} [↔]
mr _{FUFAL}	73.5 _{+9.4} ^P ↔	65.8 _{+3.9} ^{IP} ↔	72.7 _{+6.9} [↔]	72.3 _{+8.2} ^P ↔	64.9 _{+4.8} ^{2P} ↔	71.1 _{+5.3} [↔]
es _{ANC}	84.9 _{+17.0} ^P ↔	85.4 _{+2.2} ^{IP} ↔	85.2 _{+2.3} [↔]	88.4 _{+20.5} ^P ↔	87.6 _{+8.4} ^{IP} ↔	85.6 _{+2.7} [↔]
ta _{TTB}	68.5 _{+9.4} ^P ↔	62.4 _{+4.9} ^{IP} ↔	67.0 _{+2.7} [↔]	69.9 _{+10.8} ^P ↔	64.9 _{+2.4} ^{IP} ↔	71.9 _{+2.2} [↔]
te _{MTG}	85.0 _{+11.2} ^P ↔	85.0 _{+0.0} ^{2P} ↔	87.4 _{+7.0} [↔]	86.7 _{+12.9} ^P ↔	89.6 _{+4.6} ^{IP} ↔	90.0 _{+9.6} [↔]
vi _{VTB}	66.6 _{+9.3} ^P ↔	63.8 _{+0.7} ^{2P} ↔	64.0 _{+0.5} [↔]	68.3 _{+11.0} ^P ↔	65.1 _{+0.6} ^{2P} ↔	65.2 _{+0.7} [↔]
μ	77.9 _{+12.6}	77.8 _{+2.4}	78.6 _{+3.8}	79.9 _{+14.6}	80.0 _{+4.6}	79.7 _{+4.9}

Table 2: UAS scores with delay 1 and 2. Notation as in Table 1. Subscripts denote performance boost over zero-delay fully incremental results from Table 1.

ments, even for long-distance dependencies.

5 Conclusion

We evaluated modern neural NLP architectures for incremental dependency parsing across multiple languages, using various encoders and decoders. We have found that said architectures are not adequate to model incrementality, at least in the absence of specific adaptations. Strongly incremental models with no delay yield accuracies about 10 points below competitive non-incremental baselines. While this gap narrows when adding a 2-

Figure 1: Displacement performance (English above, Chinese below) for the (fully incremental) models specified in Table 1 with delay zero (solid lines) and two (dashed lines). Different symbols and colors denote forward-looking (■), non-forward looking (○) and transition-based (☆) decoders. DM^{∞} performance is included with gray dotted lines.

word lookahead, it is still about 5 points, contrasting with the situation in pre-deep-learning times, when incremental parsers were competitive (cf. (Zhang and Nivre, 2011)). The results suggest that much of the accuracy improvements in parsing obtained in recent years hinge on bidirectionality, deviating from human processing.

Accurate incremental parsing should in theory be possible (as the human example shows). Incremental processing is useful both for practical applications (Köhn, 2019), specially those involving real-time speech (Coman et al., 2019; Ekstedt and Skantze, 2021); as well as for cognitive modeling (Demberg and Keller, 2019; Stanojević et al., 2021). Thus, we believe that designing architectures that work well in a strongly incremental setting is an important open challenge in NLP. In this respect, techniques like using tentative predictions of future words made by autoregressive language models as a substitute for delay (Madureira and Schlangen, 2020) might be helpful. It is also conceivable that accuracy losses might not be solvable by better unidirectional scoring systems, and thus alternatives such as better search or methods that revise earlier decisions are also worth exploring.

Limitations

Limited physical resources We have no access to large computing infrastructures or a budget to scale services in the cloud. We had access to a few internal servers, for a total of 6 NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 (24GB each), and temporally we also obtained access to a NVIDIA A100 GPU (80GB), as well as a workstation for quick debugging. This restricts the number and size of models that we can try. In particular, we could train in reasonable amounts of time the smallest BLOOM language model (560M parameters). It was possible for us to fit up to the 3B version on the A100 GPU with a minimal batch size, but the amount of time that it took to train a model made it unfeasible to carry out a multilingual study like the one proposed in this work. Still, preliminary results showed that these larger BLOOM models were not contributing to significantly improve the performance. In this respect, we know that scaling *a lot* can play an important role, and that the standard BLOOM model is the 176B version. However, a model of that size is completely out of our economic and computing resources. Yet, we feel our study with smaller models is equally, or even more relevant, since it represents effectively the resources at hand for most companies and academic institutions.

Delay parameter Incremental parsers have a *delay* parameter that models how far beyond word i the parser can access to generate a partial parse for $w_1 \dots w_i$. For our main experiment we set the delay to 0, although we also provide results with delay 1 and 2. If we aim for psycholinguistic plausibility, there cannot be a single one-size-fits-all value for the delay, as the time taken by humans to parse linguistic input can be influenced by various factors like language, word length, reading/speaking speed, language proficiency, etc.; so any choice of delay is necessarily a simplification. However, evidence seems to point to human parsing generally being very fast, with latencies in the range of 100-250 ms (see for example Pulvermüller et al. (2009); Bemis and Pykkänen (2011)). Hence our choice of delay 0 as the safest option, and we also present experiments with 1 and 2 to show what happens when a small lag between the input and the parse is accounted for.

Scope of definition Our definition of strong incrementality only applies to monotonic parsers. This is a deliberate choice: if we allowed non-

monotonicity (i.e., removing or modifying dependencies from previous partial parses), then the definition would allow for a hypothetical parser that removes all partial output upon reading the last word and replaces it with a brand new parse generated with access to the whole sentence, which would be incremental in name only and render any comparison between incremental and non-incremental parsers moot.

While there might be alternative ways to restrict the definition to avoid this problem (e.g. restrict each step to be $O(1)$), these would come with their own limitations (e.g., excluding neural architectures where obtaining each word’s vector representation is $O(n)$, or transition-based parsers with quadratic complexities). Thus, we believe that our definition is a good compromise for our purposes, as it is simple, unambiguous and implementation-independent within the realm of monotonic parsing.

Comparing non-monotonic parsers is a different undertaking as it not only would require a different definition of incrementality, but also evaluation metrics focused on partial parse accuracy rather than final LAS/UAS. But that is orthogonal to comparing incremental to non-incremental parsers (as partial parse accuracy is not even well-defined for some non-incremental parsers that do not have intermediate states) and lies outside the scope of this paper.

Differences in incremental processing between humans and machines

Currently, despite research efforts, a comprehensive understanding of why humans excel at incremental processing compared to machines remains elusive. This issue also constrains our options for analysis. In this regard, the proficiency of humans at incremental language processing likely stems from adaptation in the context of cognitive constraints, having to understand real-time input with limited working memory which forces eager processing (see e.g. [Christiansen and Chater 2016](#)). From a different perspective, [Wilcox et al. \(2021\)](#) showed that both humans and models exhibit increased processing difficulty in ungrammatical sentences. However, language models consistently underestimate the magnitude of this difficulty compared to humans, particularly in predicting longer reaction times for syntactic violations.

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A Appendix

A.1 Additional results

Tables 3 and 4 show the aggregate results according to LAS. Tables 5 to 16 illustrate the performance of every individual encoder-decoder pair in each treebank test set.

	Fully incremental			Incremental decoder			DM	
	fl	non-fl	tb	fl	non-fl	tb	↔	↻
arPADT	70.1 _R [→]	70.5 _{IP} [↻]	69.5 _↻	79.0 _R [↻]	82.3 _{2P} [↻]	78.9 _↻	81.4	85.9
euBDT	56.4 _P [↻]	63.0 _{IP} [↻]	60.4 _↻	82.1 _R [↻]	84.4 _{2P} [↻]	76.0 _↻	82.4	85.0
zhGSD	43.9 _R [→]	51.4 _{2P} [↻]	54.6 _↻	80.5 _R [↻]	84.1 _{IP} [↻]	77.5 _↻	83.9	87.6
enEWT	59.0 _P [→]	67.5 _{IP} [↻]	65.4 _↻	87.9 _R [↻]	89.1 _{IP} [↻]	84.5 _↻	88.0	90.1
frGSD	67.1 _R [→]	78.2 _{2P} [↻]	78.1 _↻	90.0 _A [↻]	92.4 _{2P} [↻]	87.0 _↻	90.0	92.1
hiHDTB	60.7 _P [→]	69.6 _{2P} [↻]	73.1 _↻	91.3 _A [↻]	92.3 _{2P} [↻]	86.0 _↻	92.6	92.4
idGSD	68.2 _R [→]	72.1 _{IP} [↻]	67.7 _↻	79.5 _R [↻]	79.2 _{2P} [↻]	73.5 _↻	83.2	82.5
mrUFAL	48.3 _P [↻]	45.9 _{IP} [↻]	36.4 _↻	64.6 _P [↻]	62.6 _{IP} [↻]	61.6 _↻	59.6	72.8
esANC	63.8 _R [→]	78.9 _{2P} [↻]	76.3 _↻	90.0 _A [↻]	91.6 _{2P} [↻]	85.5 _↻	89.6	92.3
taTTB	50.6 _P [→]	52.6 _{IP} [↻]	42.7 _↻	62.3 _R [↻]	66.3 _{2P} [↻]	64.8 _↻	66.2	68.9
teMTG	65.6 _P [↻]	67.3 _{IP} [↻]	53.5 _↻	79.8 _R [↻]	81.7 _{IP} [↻]	64.6 _↻	69.4	87.5
viVTB	45.5 _R [→]	50.8 _{2P} [↻]	43.8 _↻	60.3 _R [↻]	61.5 _{2P} [↻]	56.8 _↻	62.9	67.3
μ	58.3	64.0	60.1	78.9	80.6	74.7	79.1	83.7

Table 3: LAS scores. Notation comes from Table 1.

	Fully incremental delay 1			Fully incremental delay 2		
	fl	non-fl	tb	fl	non-fl	tb
arPADT	78.8 _{+3.7} ^P	74.6 _{+4.1} ^{2P}	68.1 _{+1.4} [↻]	78.3 _{+8.2} ^P	77.1 _{+6.6} ^{IP}	68.7 _{+0.8} [↻]
euBDT	73.5 _{+17.1} ^P	71.2 _{+8.2} ^{IP}	59.4 _{+1.0} [↻]	75.2 _{+18.8} ^{IP}	75.2 _{+12.2} ^{IP}	63.6 _{+3.2} [↻]
zhGSD	60.4 _{+16.5} ^P	68.3 _{+16.9} ^{2P}	61.3 _{+6.7} [↻]	64.6 _{+20.7} ^P	69.7 _{+18.3} ^{2P}	75.6 _{+21.0} [↻]
enEWT	79.1 _{+20.1} ^P	84.2 _{+16.7} ^{IP}	83.3 _{+17.9} [↻]	83.0 _{+24.0} ^P	85.0 _{+17.5} ^{IP}	85.2 _{+19.8} [↻]
frGSD	80.9 _{+13.8} ^P	81.9 _{+3.7} ^{2P}	76.0 _{+2.1} [↻]	84.2 _{+17.1} ^{IP}	85.4 _{+7.2} ^{IP}	75.9 _{+2.2} [↻]
hiHDTB	78.1 _{+17.4} ^P	79.6 _{+10.0} ^{IP}	77.4 _{+4.3} [↻]	82.0 _{+21.3} ^P	84.9 _{+15.3} ^{IP}	77.4 _{+4.3} [↻]
idGSD	73.0 _{+5.4} ^P	72.3 _{+0.2} ^{IP}	66.9 _{+0.8} [↻]	75.2 _{+7.0} ^{IP}	74.6 _{+2.5} ^{2P}	68.3 _{+0.6} [↻]
mrUFAL	58.2 _{+9.9} ^P	54.4 _{+8.5} ^{2P}	72.7 _{+36.3} [↻]	57.4 _{+9.1} ^P	51.2 _{+5.3} ^{2P}	66.8 _{+30.4} [↻]
esANC	82.4 _{+18.6} ^P	82.7 _{+3.8} ^{IP}	85.2 _{+8.9} [↻]	86.2 _{+22.4} ^P	85.0 _{+6.1} ^{IP}	85.6 _{+9.3} [↻]
taTTB	56.4 _{+5.8} ^P	50.3 _{+2.3} ^{IP}	67.0 _{+24.3} [↻]	58.2 _{+7.6} ^P	53.8 _{+1.2} ^{IP}	51.8 _{+9.1} [↻]
teMTG	76.2 _{+10.9} ^P	74.1 _{+6.8} ^{IP}	87.4 _{+33.9} [↻]	76.8 _{+11.2} ^P	79.4 _{+12.1} ^{IP}	48.0 _{+5.5} [↻]
viVTB	53.6 _{+8.1} ^P	50.2 _{+0.6} ^{2P}	63.2 _{+19.4} [↻]	54.4 _{+8.9} ^P	51.2 _{+0.3} ^{2P}	45.9 _{+2.1} [↻]
μ	71.0 _{+12.7}	70.3 _{+6.3}	72.3 _{+12.2}	73.0 _{+14.7}	72.7 _{+8.7}	67.7 _{+7.6}

Table 4: LAS scores with delay one and two. Notation comes from Table 2.

A.2 Training hyperparameters and model configuration

Table 17 shows the hyperparameters selected in the training process of each encoder. For LSTMs and BiLSTMs, words and PoS tags were mapped to a 300-dimensional and 100-dimensional vector representation, respectively. Word information at the character level was represented with the last hidden state of dimension 100 from a charLSTM. These three representations were concatenated and projected to the encoder hidden size. For pretrained encoders (BLOOM, mGPT and XLM-RoBERTa), we get their last layer representations. Then, they are linearly projected to a smaller dimensionality of size 100.

Table 18 shows the training configuration per architecture: LSTM and BiLSTM weights were fitted with Adam optimizer ($\beta_0 = 0.9$, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\varepsilon = 1e-12$) and pretrained encoders with AdamW ($\beta_0 = 0.9$, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\varepsilon = 1e-12$). Batch size was adapted by the number of parameters of the encoders and the size of the treebank: in small en-

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB	
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p		
UAS	LSTM	71.7	75.7	59.9	74.1	73.0	78.2	
		74.8	80.2	81.3	76.9	76.2	76.9	
		72.6	81.4	81.6	79.2	78.5	77.3	
		mGPT	52.6	74.7	59.5	76.8	76.4	78.4
		65.5	81.7	84.2	80.0	80.2	79.9	
		63.8	82.3	83.6	82.9	82.4	80.0	
	BLOOM	43.0	74.4	58.6	75.6	75.6	79.6	
	56.5	81.1	82.8	79.7	79.3	79.1		
	55.4	81.5	83.9	81.9	82.0	79.9		
	BiLSTM	71.0	83.2	65.9	81.3	80.4	82.0	
	75.2	83.3	83.0	82.1	81.0	78.7		
	73.0	83.4	82.9	82.3	81.1	78.3		
XLM	77.2	84.6	66.1	87.2	88.0	86.9		
86.1	87.9	86.0	89.6	88.8	83.1			
84.4	87.1	88.8	89.2	89.2	83.8			
DM		87.3						
LAS	LSTM	67.1	70.1	55.9	68.8	67.8	66.3	
		68.6	73.5	74.9	71.0	69.6	59.6	
		66.4	74.7	75.1	73.0	72.0	60.7	
		mGPT	48.9	68.8	55.3	70.5	70.4	69.5
		61.2	76.0	78.8	74.1	74.6	68.1	
		59.6	76.8	78.3	77.1	77.0	68.7	
	BLOOM	39.6	67.6	54.4	68.9	68.8	67.6	
	52.4	75.2	77.3	73.6	73.4	67.2		
	51.3	75.7	78.0	76.0	75.9	67.8		
	BiLSTM	66.8	77.6	61.9	76.1	75.2	73.4	
	69.6	76.6	76.4	75.8	74.7	62.8		
	67.6	76.6	76.3	76.0	74.6	61.9		
XLM	72.5	79.0	62.7	81.6	82.3	78.9		
80.9	82.3	81.0	84.5	83.7	68.6			
79.6	82.0	83.9	84.1	83.8	71.8			
DM		81.8						

Table 5: UAS and LAS for the Arabic PADT treebank. Last index level corresponds to delay results. First, second and third subrow show the scores obtained with 0, 1 and 2-delay, respectively.

coders (LSTMs and BiLSTMs) data was distributed in batches of size 600, while pretrained encoders were trained with batches of size 2000.

A.3 Other statistics about the treebanks

Table 19 shows treebank language abbreviations and the percentage of arcs that point to the left and to the right in each treebank.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	59.4	61.7	61.9	72.0	71.7	69.7
		69.0	70.8	74.0	70.8	0.0	73.6
		68.5	73.9	75.7	72.9	74.1	75.5
	mGPT	42.0	55.0	62.0	73.0	72.9	71.0
		58.5	67.7	78.4	76.9	76.0	75.7
		59.6	72.3	80.0	80.1	79.5	76.9
	BLOOM	34.6	50.7	58.1	64.3	65.2	63.4
		48.9	60.8	73.8	68.8	68.2	72.1
		52.6	67.8	75.9	74.7	72.2	74.6
	BiLSTM	81.5	87.0	73.3	83.6	83.7	83.3
		72.6	78.5	78.0	71.3	71.0	77.5
		70.7	79.6	77.3	71.8	70.6	76.7
	XLM	80.9	83.6	73.7	87.6	87.6	86.6
		84.8	86.4	86.2	86.4	85.8	84.4
		84.9	85.5	85.2	86.0	85.6	85.4
	DM	84.8					
LAS	LSTM	53.5	55.7	55.3	60.7	60.1	52.0
		61.6	63.7	67.3	63.5	0.0	52.8
		61.6	66.7	69.3	66.0	67.3	55.2
	mGPT	38.4	49.6	56.4	63.0	62.7	60.4
		54.4	63.2	73.5	71.2	70.4	59.4
		55.5	67.8	75.2	75.2	74.4	63.6
	BLOOM	30.8	44.2	51.4	53.3	54.2	50.1
		43.8	54.8	66.9	61.9	60.9	55.5
		47.5	62.2	69.7	68.6	65.8	58.7
	BiLSTM	76.5	82.1	69.6	78.4	78.6	67.8
		65.1	70.0	70.5	63.8	63.9	54.6
		62.8	71.8	69.6	64.8	63.0	53.7
	XLM	78.2	80.4	71.3	84.3	84.4	76.0
		81.2	82.7	82.6	82.4	81.8	77.0
		81.1	81.6	81.5	82.3	81.5	77.7
	DM	77.3					

Table 6: UAS and LAS for the Basque BDT treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	43.7	51.1	45.0	62.9	61.9	60.1
		51.7	59.8	61.3	62.0	60.7	69.6
		54.6	64.3	64.0	65.3	64.6	70.9
	mGPT	33.8	47.6	44.7	63.4	63.6	64.1
		43.3	57.4	64.3	72.6	73.5	72.8
		40.5	63.0	67.4	73.6	74.8	75.6
	BLOOM	23.7	45.0	44.4	63.8	64.4	60.4
		32.5	57.3	64.2	71.5	71.9	71.4
		37.9	62.8	68.4	72.9	71.7	73.2
	BiLSTM	69.1	81.6	63.9	79.8	79.8	77.7
		62.5	72.8	71.7	69.1	67.9	72.5
		59.8	73.1	72.5	68.9	67.8	71.0
	XLM	81.6	83.4	65.3	87.5	87.3	85.3
		85.2	83.6	85.5	86.7	87.1	83.5
		85.3	85.4	83.4	86.6	85.8	81.8
	DM	85.3					
LAS	LSTM	37.5	43.9	42.0	50.5	49.4	50.2
		46.7	54.0	56.0	56.5	54.7	49.8
		49.5	58.3	58.6	59.3	58.5	52.9
	mGPT	29.7	40.6	41.5	51.1	51.4	54.6
		40.2	53.5	60.0	67.5	68.3	61.0
		37.8	59.3	63.6	68.9	69.7	75.6
	BLOOM	19.7	37.2	40.5	50.6	51.3	47.9
		29.9	53.5	60.4	66.0	66.4	61.3
		35.0	58.7	64.6	68.0	66.3	63.9
	BiLSTM	66.3	78.5	61.8	76.7	76.6	71.4
		56.4	66.2	66.4	64.1	61.9	55.1
		54.1	66.6	67.1	63.4	62.0	55.4
	XLM	78.8	80.5	63.6	84.1	84.1	77.5
		82.3	80.6	82.8	83.7	84.3	74.2
		82.2	82.2	81.0	83.3	82.2	72.4
	DM	82.4					

Table 7: UAS and LAS for the Chinese GSD treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	58.8	60.5	61.5	74.4	73.3	70.4
		75.5	78.3	77.4	82.5	81.7	79.0
		80.1	82.6	80.3	83.9	82.6	78.6
	mGPT	49.5	56.4	59.0	74.0	74.7	72.9
		73.9	78.2	81.9	88.1	87.4	83.3
		78.6	83.4	85.6	88.7	88.6	85.2
	BLOOM	44.4	54.8	59.0	73.2	72.8	69.0
		68.7	76.3	80.4	85.3	84.6	81.7
		74.0	80.8	82.2	85.7	86.4	81.3
	BiLSTM	82.4	88.9	77.4	87.1	86.0	83.5
		84.6	87.3	84.8	84.6	83.7	80.5
		84.7	86.8	85.1	84.7	84.0	79.1
	XLM	88.6	90.1	78.3	91.6	91.0	89.5
		89.9	92.9	90.7	92.6	91.2	89.4
		92.2	92.5	92.6	93.1	92.8	86.4
	DM	90.6					
	LAS	LSTM	55.0	56.8	59.0	67.5	66.3
71.3			73.8	73.9	77.7	77.1	62.9
76.0			78.5	76.6	79.4	78.6	64.6
mGPT		46.0	52.3	55.7	65.7	66.2	65.4
		70.9	74.9	79.1	84.2	83.5	83.3
		75.4	80.2	83.0	85.0	84.8	85.2
BLOOM		41.0	50.2	55.1	64.0	63.9	58.3
		64.1	72.4	76.2	80.7	79.4	68.4
		70.4	76.3	78.6	81.4	81.9	70.6
BiLSTM		80.1	86.6	75.7	84.9	83.6	76.2
		80.7	83.6	81.3	80.5	79.7	66.8
		80.7	82.9	81.7	81.0	80.1	65.4
XLM		86.5	87.9	76.4	89.1	88.5	84.5
		86.8	90.5	88.7	90.2	88.6	74.4
		89.9	90.1	90.4	90.9	90.5	74.2
DM		88.5					

Table 8: UAS and LAS for the English EWT treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	69.2	70.9	67.0	82.2	81.6	84.7
		77.5	79.4	80.3	80.9	81.6	84.4
		81.0	83.3	83.1	84.5	84.5	84.3
	mGPT	57.9	68.3	67.4	84.4	84.2	84.1
		73.8	79.8	84.4	85.8	86.2	87.5
		78.0	83.6	87.6	89.2	88.8	86.3
	BLOOM	54.1	68.0	66.1	82.8	82.2	83.8
		69.2	78.5	82.3	85.0	84.7	85.8
		72.0	82.8	86.7	87.0	86.8	86.7
	BiLSTM	85.3	91.4	80.1	89.8	89.0	88.8
		84.7	88.4	87.6	87.6	86.7	84.6
		85.0	87.8	87.6	87.2	86.8	85.5
	XLM	92.3	92.2	80.7	94.5	94.7	91.6
		93.0	93.4	93.5	93.8	94.4	90.2
		94.4	93.8	92.4	93.5	93.9	89.7
	DM	93.3					
	LAS	LSTM	65.4	67.1	63.4	75.8	75.3
72.1			74.3	75.1	75.1	75.5	66.6
75.5			78.2	78.3	79.0	79.0	68.6
mGPT		54.9	64.7	63.8	78.2	78.2	78.1
		70.6	76.4	80.9	81.4	81.9	76.0
		74.9	80.6	84.2	85.4	85.3	75.9
BLOOM		50.6	63.9	62.5	76.4	75.6	73.6
		65.7	74.4	78.7	79.8	79.7	73.3
		68.5	78.8	83.2	82.0	82.0	74.4
BiLSTM		82.0	87.7	77.2	86.2	85.5	82.0
		79.4	83.2	82.5	82.4	81.6	71.1
		79.7	82.2	82.5	82.1	81.5	71.9
XLM		90.0	89.9	79.1	92.0	92.4	87.0
		90.2	90.7	90.7	91.1	91.7	79.8
		91.6	91.0	89.8	90.9	90.9	78.4
DM		89.6					

Table 9: UAS and LAS for the French GSD treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	f1			non-f1		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	66.0	66.1	67.1	82.8	82.7	83.2
		73.0	74.5	81.4	81.1	80.8	87.6
		76.8	78.7	84.1	86.0	86.1	88.9
	mGPT	46.2	62.4	66.1	83.5	83.4	82.3
		67.7	72.4	82.5	86.2	85.8	88.7
		73.0	77.6	85.8	90.1	89.6	88.1
	BLOOM	48.0	61.6	64.9	80.8	81.2	81.7
		61.9	70.3	81.9	84.2	83.9	88.3
		64.7	75.1	85.1	88.2	88.0	88.8
	BiLSTM	91.5	94.2	78.2	93.3	93.3	92.8
		87.8	91.2	90.4	88.2	87.8	90.7
		88.1	91.4	91.1	87.5	87.0	89.6
	XLM	94.3	93.5	78.0	94.7	95.3	93.8
		94.6	94.1	92.7	93.7	94.2	94.1
		95.0	94.2	92.6	94.0	94.2	93.8
	DM			95.5			
LAS	LSTM	60.0	60.4	60.7	67.8	67.8	71.3
		67.8	69.4	76.3	74.1	73.8	72.0
		72.4	74.2	79.4	80.3	80.4	74.4
	mGPT	41.5	57.0	60.5	69.2	69.6	73.1
		64.0	68.5	78.1	79.6	79.1	77.4
		69.2	73.8	82.0	84.9	84.1	77.4
	BLOOM	43.4	55.0	57.5	65.4	66.0	69.2
		57.6	66.1	77.6	77.1	77.1	74.5
		61.0	71.0	80.7	82.7	82.2	74.1
	BiLSTM	88.5	91.2	75.6	90.4	90.3	83.8
		83.0	86.4	85.9	83.7	83.2	75.5
		83.4	86.6	86.7	82.8	82.2	75.2
	XLM	91.3	90.5	75.7	91.8	92.3	86.0
		91.3	90.9	89.8	90.3	90.8	85.8
		91.8	90.8	89.7	90.5	90.8	88.2
	DM			92.7			

Table 10: UAS and LAS for the Hindi HDTB treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	f1			non-f1		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	70.4	73.0	57.5	77.9	77.3	78.6
		78.3	79.2	80.6	77.6	76.4	79.2
		75.9	80.2	81.4	79.7	80.0	79.5
	mGPT	46.0	67.5	56.0	77.2	77.0	76.0
		60.6	75.5	80.8	80.4	80.2	78.8
		62.0	77.7	81.9	82.0	82.1	79.6
	BLOOM	40.4	66.2	55.9	75.9	75.9	78.4
		55.8	73.6	80.6	78.0	77.6	77.2
		56.0	76.2	80.5	80.1	80.4	77.9
	BiLSTM	73.9	84.5	67.6	81.5	83.8	84.7
		79.0	83.6	82.4	82.2	79.9	78.3
		76.5	82.5	82.7	80.9	80.8	80.1
	XLM	75.5	82.9	65.4	86.2	86.3	85.1
		83.7	86.0	87.2	87.5	87.1	83.0
		83.4	85.6	84.6	87.6	87.2	83.2
	DM			88.6			
LAS	LSTM	65.7	68.2	53.8	72.1	71.6	67.7
		69.9	70.8	72.3	69.2	68.8	59.4
		68.6	72.4	73.4	72.0	71.9	59.7
	mGPT	40.9	60.1	50.6	67.3	67.6	64.9
		54.8	68.5	73.6	72.3	71.8	66.9
		56.5	70.7	75.2	74.2	74.6	68.3
	BLOOM	35.8	58.6	49.7	66.2	66.1	63.3
		50.0	66.1	73.2	69.3	68.9	64.3
		50.4	68.5	73.4	72.0	71.8	65.8
	BiLSTM	69.7	79.5	64.8	73.4	78.8	73.5
		71.0	75.3	74.1	73.3	71.7	61.9
		68.7	74.1	75.0	72.4	72.6	62.4
	XLM	69.5	76.1	61.5	78.8	79.2	71.7
		77.3	78.8	80.6	80.3	79.7	71.1
		76.9	78.8	79.0	80.8	80.3	70.7
	DM			83.6			

Table 11: UAS and LAS for the Indonesian GSD treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	42.7	55.3	64.1	65.0	69.7	65.8
		54.7	63.0	65.2	58.4	62.8	69.9
		60.8	64.2	60.6	63.1	60.1	71.1
	mGPT	27.2	45.2	59.2	63.1	61.2	60.7
		39.2	58.2	66.8	65.8	61.5	72.7
		37.4	58.1	68.9	63.1	64.4	66.8
	BLOOM	28.9	45.6	59.0	59.7	58.2	60.0
		46.7	55.1	73.5	62.3	64.9	69.2
		43.3	58.7	72.3	61.0	64.9	69.0
	BiLSTM	60.4	75.7	69.7	75.2	73.8	76.0
		60.2	69.3	67.8	63.9	61.6	66.6
		58.8	66.3	65.8	55.5	65.1	67.4
	XLM	33.7	63.4	70.4	71.4	71.8	73.5
		54.5	69.7	78.6	72.1	73.6	79.7
		52.8	74.7	79.4	80.0	68.0	80.2
	DM			82.4			
	LAS	LSTM	34.0	43.9	47.8	44.2	45.9
39.8			48.8	50.2	44.0	48.4	38.3
43.9			50.3	46.6	43.8	44.7	40.2
mGPT		21.8	34.2	48.3	45.9	45.6	36.4
		31.5	45.3	50.9	53.0	48.0	72.7
		27.4	45.5	55.4	49.9	51.2	66.8
BLOOM		23.8	34.5	48.3	44.4	41.5	28.2
		36.8	44.7	58.2	49.8	54.4	42.4
		33.7	46.6	57.4	49.9	49.2	42.8
BiLSTM		47.6	60.0	57.3	59.0	59.2	49.3
		44.0	51.8	44.8	44.9	44.3	42.6
		42.4	49.8	47.3	42.4	45.3	30.8
XLM		30.6	55.3	64.6	62.6	62.4	61.6
		49.1	58.0	66.5	61.2	60.8	64.4
		45.9	64.2	65.4	69.8	55.2	55.6
DM				62.5			

Table 12: UAS and LAS for the Marathi UFAL treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	67.4	67.9	64.7	80.4	79.9	82.3
		75.9	78.6	80.6	79.2	78.3	82.8
		77.7	82.0	84.0	82.1	82.0	83.5
	mGPT	62.0	66.4	65.4	82.4	83.2	82.9
		73.0	79.8	84.9	85.4	84.8	85.2
		76.2	83.5	88.4	87.6	87.2	85.6
	BLOOM	53.1	66.7	65.1	81.0	81.4	81.7
		67.7	78.4	83.9	83.7	83.6	84.2
		70.3	82.3	87.1	85.7	85.8	85.2
	BiLSTM	88.4	89.6	79.1	88.5	87.4	88.0
		84.8	87.4	88.2	86.3	85.9	84.5
		87.8	87.1	87.6	85.8	85.8	83.8
	XLM	92.0	91.5	80.5	93.4	93.4	91.2
		93.8	93.0	94.2	93.6	93.4	88.7
		93.9	93.0	92.7	93.6	93.6	88.6
	DM			93.1			
	LAS	LSTM	63.7	63.8	61.6	75.3	74.6
71.2			74.0	76.1	74.4	73.8	67.0
73.1			77.3	79.8	77.8	77.6	68.5
mGPT		59.3	63.1	62.9	78.0	78.9	76.3
		70.5	77.2	82.4	82.7	82.0	85.2
		73.6	80.9	86.2	85.0	84.5	85.6
BLOOM		50.3	63.2	62.2	76.0	76.2	74.5
		65.1	75.3	81.0	80.4	80.3	72.3
		67.5	79.2	84.6	82.5	82.2	74.2
BiLSTM		84.9	86.2	76.3	85.3	84.0	80.9
		80.4	83.1	84.1	82.1	81.7	71.3
		82.9	82.7	83.4	81.7	81.5	71.2
XLM		90.0	89.7	79.2	91.4	91.6	85.5
		91.6	91.0	92.3	91.6	91.4	78.2
		91.7	90.8	90.9	91.6	91.5	76.4
DM				82.4			

Table 13: UAS and LAS for the Spanish ANCORA treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	39.4	55.7	59.1	67.3	66.0	69.7
		42.5	50.7	54.3	54.4	43.5	61.7
		46.5	57.1	56.0	53.7	50.8	61.2
	mGPT	20.3	48.7	55.8	64.1	62.8	65.2
		32.1	57.7	68.3	62.0	60.3	67.0
		28.7	60.9	69.9	54.1	55.1	66.9
	BLOOM	19.4	49.4	54.0	55.8	63.1	65.7
		28.6	56.0	68.5	62.4	58.8	66.7
		31.6	60.0	64.9	64.9	63.6	71.9
	BiLSTM	51.2	71.4	61.7	74.3	74.7	73.7
		51.8	57.0	63.3	57.6	57.8	64.0
		45.1	57.3	64.2	58.2	56.4	65.6
	XLM	28.9	65.9	62.4	75.8	74.6	78.6
		41.0	69.6	72.2	71.8	72.4	74.4
		39.7	68.3	75.5	74.3	71.2	75.6
	DM			75.8			
	LAS	LSTM	33.2	44.8	50.6	52.6	51.3
28.3			35.6	40.3	38.6	22.5	32.4
30.7			40.1	42.4	38.3	36.7	29.6
mGPT		15.7	37.6	44.6	47.5	46.5	42.7
		25.8	47.4	56.4	50.3	48.4	67.0
		22.8	49.5	58.2	41.6	43.1	44.7
BLOOM		15.4	37.2	42.9	38.6	46.8	40.3
		22.7	45.0	56.2	50.1	47.2	45.2
		25.9	48.5	52.1	53.8	50.3	51.8
BiLSTM		44.9	62.3	47.0	65.7	66.3	57.5
		38.0	40.9	45.6	41.1	42.9	32.5
		31.5	39.5	47.8	41.1	41.4	35.4
XLM		24.9	56.8	55.0	65.6	64.7	64.8
		34.7	59.4	61.7	60.8	61.7	53.2
		33.2	58.0	65.2	63.7	61.2	55.7
DM				65.5			

Table 14: UAS and LAS for the Tamil TTB treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	fl			non-fl		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	64.6	67.6	73.8	84.7	85.0	80.4
		78.6	78.3	78.4	82.2	83.5	87.3
		78.3	83.1	82.5	83.9	85.0	90.0
	mGPT	55.5	59.1	71.8	82.0	81.6	75.6
		73.7	75.0	85.0	84.5	85.0	87.4
		80.2	82.7	86.7	89.6	84.2	80.8
	BLOOM	51.7	54.8	70.0	79.1	79.2	74.1
		72.4	73.6	84.3	84.5	82.9	87.2
		78.7	78.2	85.7	84.0	84.0	87.8
	BiLSTM	86.3	89.9	85.3	90.2	90.3	89.0
		71.8	88.1	86.7	80.0	84.5	81.0
		71.3	88.1	85.0	83.2	76.2	82.4
	XLM	77.8	87.4	84.9	89.6	89.2	88.9
		83.6	88.2	89.9	86.7	87.0	84.2
		68.6	90.7	91.5	89.0	88.3	91.7
	DM			89.7			
	LAS	LSTM	57.8	59.9	64.8	66.6	67.0
68.6			67.0	67.0	62.9	63.2	52.3
47.7			70.6	69.7	60.8	67.6	48.0
mGPT		49.4	51.6	65.6	67.3	67.1	50.5
		65.6	67.1	76.5	74.1	71.3	87.4
		71.7	74.1	76.8	79.4	74.8	25.4
BLOOM		46.5	45.4	62.1	63.8	63.4	43.4
		66.0	64.8	74.2	72.2	71.7	54.3
		71.8	68.7	74.3	74.2	67.4	47.9
BiLSTM		74.9	77.7	76.7	79.6	79.6	64.6
		52.2	70.4	70.5	60.2	64.9	47.1
		52.5	73.9	64.9	60.8	55.0	56.5
XLM		72.3	79.8	79.5	81.7	81.1	61.3
		75.5	79.2	80.4	71.2	67.5	35.7
		51.9	82.2	83.6	77.2	78.9	55.9
DM				61.8			

Table 15: UAS and LAS for the Telugu MTG treebank. Notation comes from Table 5.

Metric	Encoder	f1			non-f1		TB
		abs-idx	rel-idx	PoS-idx	1p	2p	
UAS	LSTM	52.8	57.3	53.9	63.2	64.5	64.5
		49.2	57.8	58.2	57.2	56.7	60.9
		50.2	59.8	60.0	59.6	57.4	61.9
	mGPT	29.3	49.6	51.6	61.8	61.3	59.7
		34.8	56.9	66.6	62.9	63.8	63.2
		34.3	60.1	68.3	63.7	65.1	65.2
	BLOOM	31.7	51.0	51.1	62.1	60.7	61.0
		38.5	57.3	63.4	60.5	60.9	64.0
		38.8	61.6	64.6	59.4	62.0	60.0
	BiLSTM	66.8	72.7	64.0	70.1	70.5	71.0
		57.5	64.6	62.9	60.0	61.1	61.8
		56.2	64.3	62.5	60.2	60.0	60.9
	XLM	48.1	68.8	64.4	74.1	73.8	76.0
		58.1	68.6	73.2	73.4	71.4	75.3
		58.2	68.1	72.6	70.8	69.8	75.0
	DM	76.6					
LAS	LSTM	41.6	45.5	44.5	49.8	50.8	43.8
		36.8	42.5	43.2	42.2	42.1	36.3
		37.5	44.0	44.8	44.4	41.8	35.6
	mGPT	23.3	36.7	41.2	47.4	46.7	39.8
		28.1	44.3	53.6	49.4	50.2	63.2
		26.8	47.0	54.4	49.9	51.2	45.9
	BLOOM	24.9	38.2	40.5	46.7	45.9	39.8
		30.2	44.3	50.6	46.4	47.5	44.3
		30.7	48.1	51.0	45.8	48.6	37.4
	BiLSTM	55.4	60.3	54.6	58.2	58.3	51.2
		44.2	49.3	48.6	45.4	45.8	38.6
		42.4	48.6	47.5	45.0	45.3	38.1
	XLM	40.4	56.8	54.8	61.4	61.5	56.8
		48.8	56.6	60.6	60.6	58.1	58.7
		48.8	55.8	60.0	57.1	56.6	57.8
	DM	61.9					

Table 16: UAS and LAS for the Vietnamese MTG tree-bank. Notation comes from Table 5.

ISO code	Language	% left-arcs	% right-arcs
arPADT	Arabic	30.46%	69.54%
euBDT	Basque	49.22%	50.78%
zhGSD	Chinese	63.67%	36.33%
enEWT	English	57.18%	42.82%
frGSD	French	54.72%	45.28%
hiHDTB	Hindi	55.6%	44.4%
inGSD	Indonesian	37.75%	62.25%
mrUFAL	Marathi	51.34%	48.66%
esANC	Spanish	54.43%	45.57%
taTTB	Tamil	68.56%	31.44%
teMTG	Telugu	54.28%	45.72%
viVTB	Vietnamese	40.99%	59.01%

Table 19: Statistics of treebanks retrieved in our multi-lingual benchmark.

Hyperparameter	Fully incremental			Non incremental	
	LSTM	BLOOM	mGPT	BiLSTM	XLM
Word emb size	300	1	1	300	1
PoS-feats emb size	100	x	x	100	x
Character emb size	50	x	x	50	x
CharLSTM hidden	100	x	x	100	x
Num. layers	4	1	1	4	1
Encoder hidden	400	100	100	400	100

Table 17: Architecture design choices for different encoders

Hyperparameter	Fully incremental			Non incremental	
	LSTM	BLOOM	mGPT	BiLSTM	XLM
lr	1e-3	5e-5	5e-5	1e-3	5e-5
optimizer	Adam	AdamW	AdamW	Adam	AdamW
decay type	Exponential	Linear	Linear	Exponential	Linear
decay value	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5
epochs	200	30	30	200	30
batch size	~6000	~2000	~500	~6000	~2000

Table 18: Training hyper-parameters for different encoders